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TIMES

THz Industrial Mesh Networks in Smart Sensing and Propagation Environments

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Roles in TIMES: Project Coordinator

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Project Overview

Project Overview

- Funding Framework: first call of EU's Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU)
 - 35 Research and Innovation (R&I) projects selected
 - TIMES is one of those funded projects in STREAM B-01-02
- TIMES run-time: 1 January 2023 – 31 December 2025
- Consortium - 10 Partners (5 EU countries):
 - **Coordinator:** CNIT (IT).
 - **Academics:** TU Braunschweig (GE), CNRS (FR), USTUTT (GE)
 - **Research institutes:** FRAUNHOFER (GE), BIREX (IT)
 - **Industries:** HUAWEI (GE), TELENOR (NO), AETNA (IT)
 - **SMEs:** ANTERAL (ES)
- Technical manager: Thomas Kürner (TUBS)

Project vision and pillars

- TIMES long-term vision:
 - Smart radio ecosystem in complex scenarios offering similar performance as wired networks.

- Pillars:

Exploiting ultra-wide bandwidth and sensing-friendly characteristics of **THz communications** as wired networks.

Deploying intelligent mesh THz networks in smart propagation environments.

Enabling high-definition **integrated communications and sensing at THz**.

- Verticals: Manufacturing (I4.0, I5.0), Healthcare, Automotive

Main Innovations

	<p>Identification of potential use cases Definition of KPIs</p>
<p>THz communications</p>	<p>Intra-device/machine and inter-device/machine THz channel measurements and modelling EM exposure characterization Ultra-Massive MIMO, fast beamforming, electromagnetic signal processing 250-300 GHz highly integrated THz RF front-ends</p>
<p>Intelligent Mesh Networking in Smart Propagation environments</p>	<p>Mesh topology with active/passive devices Efficient and reliable transmission over multiple THz links 300 GHz RIS made of metamaterials</p>
<p>Integrated sensing and communications</p>	<p>Enable see-around-the-corner functionality with RISs Enhanced localization functionalities through near-field THz propagation conditions</p>
<p>Proof-of-concept</p>	<p>Integration of THz RF front-ends, antennas, RISs Multiple THz links between static and mobile devices through direct/reflected paths</p>

Expertise of Partners in TIMES

Previous Experience: an example

Thor project <https://thorproject.eu>

- Joint EU-Japan Project
- TUBS, USTUTT, CNRS, FRAUNHOFER
- Successful PoC of a 2 x 20 Gbps bidirectional 300 GHz link over 160 m

Channel ID	Maximum performance		IEEE802.15.3d			
	-	-	44	54	25	26
$f_{IF,center}$ / GHz	79.1	79.25	85.7	79.1	84.6	84.6
$f_{RF,center}$ / GHz	301.2	304.25	302.4	300.2	305.6	307.8
Bandwidth / GHz	8.64	1.35	4.32	8.64	2.16	2.16
Data Rate / Gbit/s	32	8	9.6	25.6	9.6	11.2
Modulation Scheme	32-QAM	256-QAM	8-PSK	16-QAM	64-QAM	128-QAM
Constellation						
EVM / dB	-23.6	-30.8	-20.9	-21.4	-27.1	-30.5
SNR / dB	19.6	26.3	20.6	19	23.5	25.6

PoC: BIREX Pilot Plant

Advanced production line

- test new technologies for industrial processes
- thematic areas: additive manufacturing, robotics, Big Data and IoT.
- covered by a dedicated 27 GHz private 5G network.

Mobile Wagon

Mobile Rack

PoC: AETNA Techlab

- Large area with packaging machines and test equipments
 - To demonstrate TIMES solutions in automated packaging
 - To connect the PLCs with the edge network

AETNA Company Profile

Standardization activities

Project activities / technologies that may lead to standardization:

- Industrial simulation scenarios and KPIs
- THz channel measurements/modelling in industrial scenarios
- Technology enablers for industrial THz communications

Potential targeted standardization bodies / groups:

- **ETSI ISG THz** 5 founding members: TUBS (ISG THz Chair), HUAWEI, TELENOR, CNRS, FRAUNHOFER
- ETSI ISG RIS
- IEEE 802 SC THz
- COST-INTERACT
- **one6G** 4 founding members: CNIT, TUBS, HUAWEI, TELENOR
- 3GPP

Follow us on line

www.times6g.eu (soon)

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A Preliminary Study to Start with...

Motivation and Objective

The shift towards high frequencies makes:

- arrays become electromagnetically large (though not necessarily large in size)
- wavefronts of radiated waves are **NO LONGER** planar over antenna arrays (far-field approximation)

This opens new opportunities:

- **near-field radiative propagation** conditions
- additional **degrees-of-freedom**

Objective of this preliminary study:

- to quantify the impact of the classical far-field approximation in MU-MIMO
 - planar arrays with practically large size, when operating in 30-GHz bands

DoF in LoS communications*

$$\text{dof} = \Omega_r \frac{A_s}{\lambda^2} = \frac{A_r A_s}{\lambda^2 \Delta_z^2}$$

If $L_{s,x} = L_{s,y} = 0.2 \text{ m}$, $L_{r,x} = L_{r,y} = 2 \text{ m}$, $\Delta_z = 10$:

- dof = 16 if $\lambda = 0.01 \text{ m}$ ($f_c = 30 \text{ GHz}$)
- dof = 1600 if $\lambda = 0.001 \text{ m}$ ($f_c = 300 \text{ GHz}$)

*D. Miller "Communicating with waves between volumes" Appl. Opt. 39, 1681-1699 (2000).

System and signal model

System model

- K single-antenna UEs
- Y-polarization when traveling in Z direction
- Line-of-sight propagation

Both MMSE and MR considered

- Designed with the **exact* and far-field model**
- With far-field model both operate in **mismatched mode**

Performance metric

- SE with perfect channel state information

$$\gamma_k = \frac{p_k |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_k|^2}{\sum_{i \neq k} p_i |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_i|^2 + \sigma^2 \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2}$$

*Bjornson, Sanguinetti, [Power Scaling Laws and Near-Field Behaviors of Massive MIMO and Intelligent Reflecting Surface](#), IEEE OJCS, 2020.

Why mismatched?

- Channel estimation at high frequency (e.g., mmWave)
 - Parametrization models (pro: reduced number of parameters to estimate)
 - Typical model for communication theorists: **far-field model**

$$\mathbf{h} = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i g(\theta_i, \phi_i) \mathbf{a}(\theta_i, \phi_i) \quad \mathbf{a}(\theta_i, \phi_i) = \left[e^{j\mathbf{k}(\theta_i, \phi_i)^T \mathbf{u}_1}, \dots, e^{j\mathbf{k}(\theta_i, \phi_i)^T \mathbf{u}_M} \right]^T$$

- Instead of estimating \mathbf{h} directly, estimate the three parameters $\{\alpha_i, \theta_i, \phi_i\}$
 - To obtain \mathbf{h} , eventually used to compute combiner (MR and MMSE).
 - Inevitably **mismatched**, no matter how good $\{\alpha_i, \theta_i, \phi_i\}$ have been estimated

System parameters

Parameter	Value
BS height	10 m
Horizontal array size	0.5 m
Vertical array size	1 m
Horizontal antenna spacing	Half-wavelength
Vertical antenna spacing	2 wavelengths
Bandwidth	100 MHz
UE power	20 dBm
Carrier frequency	5 GHz, 28 GHz, 71 GHz
Noise power	-87 dBm
Cell radius	230 m

Channel gain

Interference gain with exact model @28 GHz

Interference gain with mismatched model @28 GHz

Spectral efficiency

Increasing carrier frequency has a two-fold benefit with MMSE

- the average SE increases
- the CDF with the exact model exhibits a steeper behavior (more fairness)

Spectral efficiency @28 GHz

Marginally affected up to $K = 100$

- 1500 devices/km² per channel use

Conclusions

- Time to abandon the far-field approximation **above 6 GHz**
 - Already for existing arrays, not **only for larger arrays**
 - Accurate channel models are **mandatory to avoid mismatched mode!**
- Interference-aware combining schemes (e.g. MMSE)
 - based on the radiative near-field model
 - enhance system scalability and fairness
- Trend further exacerbated when operating in the **sub-THz spectrum**
 - Accurate channel models
 - Channel estimation schemes with low complexity
 - Combining/precoding techniques with low complexity (large number of antennas)